

An analysis of Human Resource Accounting Practices in India with special reference to Steel Industry

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Abstract

The most valuable resource for every firm is its human resources. Human resource accounting assists management in making important human resource management decisions, which helps to improve overall efficiency. The current study is being conducted to learn about human resource accounting practices in the Steel Industry of India. Three years of data from the company's annual reports are used to study CCI's HRA practices. The researcher discovered a very high level of disclosure of HRA information, such as total number of employees, professional profile of employees, age wise distribution of employees, category wise distribution of employees, average age, and category wise value of human resource, reviewing the current state of intellectual capital in the knowledge management paradigms is the goal of this research. The article emphasizes the value of valuing human resources and the various approaches used by different organizations. This paper presents ideas and highlights the benefits of human resource valuation.

Keywords: Human Resource Accounting, Intangible Assets, Human Resource, Human Asset.

Introduction

Human Resource accounting is an essential asset of every company. For the good success of any organisation it is important that a company should have and effective and efficient people working in an organisation. As now a day knowledgeable person who is highly motivated are not easy to find. Because employees knowledge, experience and their creativity cannot be replaced by any machinery. Managers of every organisation should appreciate and motivate their employees as they are the human asset of an organisation. In this Global era, every company evaluate the financial performance and assets of the company but know the company also started calculating the human value by the mean of human resource accounting. With the help of the human resource accounting many companies evaluates human asset and take important decision related to human resource which directly helps the company to increase their overall company's efficiency and production. American Accounting Association defines it as "a process of classifying and calculating data about human resources and communicating this information to interested parties". Hence, human resources accounting may be defined as, "a method of calculating numerical value of a company in order to manage up with the variations in its assets. Human resource e accounting helps in both evaluating physical and human values. Expenses made on evaluating the human

resource such as cost while recruiting, selecting, and development are always charged against revenue, as these expenses are not made assets which are physical. But some changes have been made as these expenses are now considered as the capital expenditure rather than charged against revenue as they give benefit for the long period of time and they also has to be shown as an assets in the balance sheet. In 1960s concept of human resource accounting came into existence but in India now a days it has been given a huge importance to human resource accounting.

Review of Literature

1. **Susanto Yohanes and Rambano Dheo** (2022) "*The Role of HRM Factors in Improving Performance Analysis of Local Government Financial Reports*" the study aims to know the factors that affect the finance quality of the selected Government and study also reveals that LAPD performance quality of the Government of many countries such as Indonesia, South Sumatra and Musirawas is effected by the ability to tackle of HRA activities and their accounting system but not fully, mainly it is affected by human resource management.
2. **Chaya. R** (2021) "*A Study of Human Resource Accounting in the Knowledge Based Economy*" the study aims to know the importance of human resource valuation and to evaluate the current

position of intellectual capital in the knowledge management models. The study depicts that human resource accounting is very much important for any company as stakeholders need an information about the financial statements and it is necessary to manage employees' productivity.

3. **Jena Biswa Mohan, et. al** (2022) *"Human Resource Accounting and Financial Performance of Select Small-Scale Industries of Odisha: An Empirical Analysis"* this paper analyses the human resource accounting practice of industries of Odisha and also finds the effect of HRA on its financial performance. The study concludes HRA is an important factor for any business and also to calculate ROA and ROE. It also tells that small businesses need to improve their human capital by means of HRA.
4. **Alijamaan Bader** (2017) *"HUMAN RESOURCES ACCOUNTING: CONCEPTS, OBJECTIVES, MODELS AND CRITICISM"* the objectives of the paper was to know about cost and value of HRA in the company and also helps companies to take HRA decisions, the paper reveals that there is an impact of HRA on decision making and reporting also HRA is used to calculate the investments in a company's human resources may aim to get long-term profit to the business.
5. **Pralhad P Rathod and B. Sudheer Kumar** (2021) *"Human Resource Accounting And Auditing"* the main objective of the research paper was to know about the Human resource accounting and auditing, also know that how company calculates return on investment on human capital. The study concludes that the company should follow the distinct HR audit committees and if HR valuation is absent then management will know the negative effect of that and profit will get decreased.
6. **Patnaik Manaswani** (2021) *"DISCLOSURE OF HUMAN RESOURCE ACCOUNTING PRACTICES: PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTOR COMPANIES IN INDIA"* the researcher aims to disclose the human resource accounting practice of public and private companies. The study concluded that public companies give full

clarification of the disclosures of human value assets on large scale and some also do to amount of value per employee and also employee's team work and research get to know that the companies should use model for human capital valuation.

7. **Aouadi Mostafa and Khenniche Youcef** (2022) *"The importance of disclosure in human resources accounting: A normative approach"* this paper aims to maintain the relation between the organization and the human to increase the productivity of the employees, it also sees the different accounting methods used to measure human values in an organization. The study concludes that employee's play an essential role in the organization's success of economics and to maintain a good performance it is necessary to calculate Human Resource accounting.
8. **Cherian Jacob and Farouq Sherine** (2013) *"A Review of Human Resource Accounting and Organizational Performance"* this paper's main object was to calculate the human resource capital and tell how human resource helps in improving the working of an organization. The paper shows that human resource accounting is an essential part of any business and it helps in taking managerial decision and evaluation the intangible value of the firm.

Need of the Study

The Human resource accounting helps to increase the overall Companies' efficiency. It also helps to know how the human resource accounting helps in taking decision, and to evaluate the return on human value assets and it also returns the potential of human resource in a company in an economic way. It also provides us the valuation of the cost.

Research Gap

The researcher identifies that many researches have been in consideration but there were few researches on companies of Steel authority of India. And only some studies describe about how the selected companies assess the applicability of human resource accounting while taking the decision and this paper also discloses the way how selected company discloses method of human resource accounting.

Objectives of the Research

1. To study the Human Resource Accounting Practices adopted by steel Authority of India.
2. To study the Disclosure Pattern followed by the steel Authority of India.
3. To assess and to analyse the Human Resource Accounting and its applicability to HR decisions.

Research Methodology

To accomplish the objectives of the study researcher used the secondary data that has

been collected from the annual reports of the Company, magazines, newspaper etc., private & public steel company has been selected for this study on the basis of revenue as on 1st April, 2018 as per the index CNX Metal of National Stock Exchange three years data has been used for the purpose of study i.e. from financial year 2018-19 to 2020-21. This study is completely based on Secondary data.

Table 1: List of selected steel companies of India

Public Company	Revenue
SAIL	69,113.61
RINL	835,462.20
Private Company	Revenue
TATA steel	156,294.14
Vedanta	86,863.00

Analysis

Table 2: Professional Profile of the employees of CCI No. of Employees (RINL)

SR.No.	Particular	As on 31.3.2021	As on 31.3.2020	As on 31.3.2019
1.	Post Graduate Engineers	2	3	1
2.	Engineers with MBA	4	2	2
3.	Graduate Engineers	21	24	20
4.	CA/ICWA/SAS/ACS	7	8	6
5.	MBBS	0	0	1
6.	MBAs	20	22	19
7.	Engineer Diploma Holders	46	42	48
8.	Professional Diploma holders	45	48	40
9.	Post Graduate	48	52	65
10.	Graduates	155	168	149
11.	ITI Certificate holders	268	220	250
12.	Others	399	402	367
	Total	1015	991	968

Interpretation: According to the table, CCI employs a large number of people with a wide range of professional degrees. It has been found that RINL is disclosing more details about the employees which is constantly increasing throughout the consecutive years which is 2020-21 No. of employees is 1015,

2019-20 No. of employees is 991, 2018-19 No. of employees is 968 respectively mostly in Engineers Diploma Holders, Graduates, ITI Certificate holders and other category, so we can say that RINL is performing better HRA practices.

Table 3: Professional Profile of the employees of CCI No. of Employees (SAIL)

SR.No.	Particular	As on 31.3.2021	As on 31.3.2020	As on 31.3.2019
1.	Post Graduate Engineers	2	1	3
2.	Engineers with MBA	7	8	6
3.	Graduate Engineers	19	21	20
4.	CA/ICWA/SAS/ACS	5	7	6

5.	MBBS	0	0	1
6.	MBAAs	21	25	24
7.	Engineer Diploma Holders	35	38	32
8.	Professional Diploma holders	62	68	72
9.	Post Graduate	58	54	52
10.	Graduates	128	150	149
11.	ITI Certificate holders	259	219	119
12.	Others	348	312	258
	Total	944	903	742

Interpretation: According to the table, CCI employs a large number of people with a wide range of professional degrees. It has been found that SAIL is disclosing more details about the employees which is constantly increasing throughout the consecutive years which is 2020-21 No. of employees is 944,

2019-20 No. of employees is 903, 2018-19 No. of employees is 742 respectively mostly in Engineers Diploma Holders, Graduates, Post Graduates and other category, so we can say that SAIL is performing better HRA practices.

Table 4: Professional Profile of the employees of CCI No. of Employees (TATA Steel)

SR.No.	Particular	As on 31.3.2021	As on 31.3.2020	As on 31.3.2019
1.	Post Graduate Engineers	2	1	1
2.	Engineers with MBA	5	6	4
3.	Graduate Engineers	19	20	19
4.	CA/ICWA/SAS/ACS	6	5	4
5.	MBBS	1	0	0
6.	MBAAs	23	21	29
7.	Engineer Diploma Holders	40	38	34
8.	Professional Diploma holders	25	26	32
9.	Post Graduate	28	27	24
10.	Graduates	142	130	135
11.	ITI Certificate holders	209	213	250
12.	Others	415	418	312
	Total	915	905	844

Interpretation: According to the table, CCI employs a large number of people with a wide range of professional degrees. It has been found that TATA Steel is disclosing more details about the employees which is constantly increasing throughout the consecutive years which is 2020-21 No. of

employees is 915, 2019-20 No. of employees is 905, 2018-19 No. of employees is 844 respectively mostly in Engineers Diploma Holders, Graduates, Engineer with MBA and other category, so we can say that TATA Steel is performing better HRA practices.

Table 5: Professional Profile of the employees of CCI No. of Employees (Vedanta)

SR.No.	Particular	As on 31.3.2021	As on 31.3.2020	As on 31.3.2019
1.	Post Graduate Engineers	2	2	2
2.	Engineers with MBA	4	5	2
3.	Graduate Engineers	18	15	11
4.	CA/ICWA/SAS/ACS	7	5	9
5.	MBBS	0	0	1

6.	MBA's	23	22	24
7.	Engineer Diploma Holders	45	48	45
8.	Professional Diploma holders	82	89	91
9.	Post Graduate	31	29	24
10.	Graduates	138	138	135
11.	ITI Certificate holders	200	199	198
12.	Others	312	293	300
	Total	862	845	842

Interpretation: According to the table, CCI employs a large number of people with a wide range of professional degrees. It has been found that Vedanta is disclosing more details about the employees which is constantly increasing throughout the consecutive years which is 2020-21 No. of employees is 862, 2019-20 No. of employees is 845, 2018-19 No. of employees is 842 respectively mostly in Engineers Diploma Holders, Graduates and other category, so we can say that Vedanta is performing better HRA practices.

Conclusion

We can infer from the study that Human Resource Accounting should be taken more importance in other sectors as well as we can say that in steel industry it is performing well a thorough comparison is made among the public and private companies and it has been found that public companies are disclosing more detailed information about the numbers of employees in its annual reports such as total number of employees, professional profiles of employees, age-based employee distribution, category-based employee distribution, and average age of people, the value of human resources etc., than in Private companies. Overall, we can say that some firms seem to value their human resources, few actually do, and attempts to implement human resource valuation are still in the very early stages. More work must be done on both the theoretical and practical levels in order to demonstrate greater progress. It is necessary to conduct more research into valuation methods, models, and the practical implications of these, as well as to involve accounting and human resource professionals in the discussion of valuation and its application in practise.

Limitation

The research has some limitation such as The Indian Companies Act of 1956 should make HRA practices obligatory. Initiative should be taken by educational institutes,

government and professional bodies to develop an objective model for the valuation of human resource. To enhance the company's HR disclosure, several HR ratios, such as profit/human resource and human assets/total resource, should be provided. The "cost" and "value" of organization human resources are not subject to any defined standards or rules that are clear. More businesses in India are required to implement human resource accounting since it treats employees as a company asset so these are few limitations related to the present study.

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